

CONTENT OF PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT FOR THE METHODOLOGY OF PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT IN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Pragmatic competence refers to the ability to appropriately use language in various social and scientific situations. For effective professional communication, students must possess certain knowledge on the subject, and in the process of teaching English, practical use of professional knowledge is expected. Foreign language instruction includes not only understanding the literal meanings of words and grammar but also awareness of the scientific nuances of communication.

The need to enhance students' pragmatic competence and the lack of the necessary methodology based on professionally-oriented communication situations in English led to the development of this competence. However, Taro and Yul emphasize that it is preferable to use a method described as eclectic. This method represents a set of exercises and technical techniques based on different methods. It is important to highlight that for students with mixed abilities, there should be a specific pedagogical system for learning English. In the proposed method, instructors strive to make lessons engaging for all students, ensuring that pragmatic competence is learned in harmony with modern demands. Pragmatic competence encompasses a system of relationships that includes organizations and fields interacting with the external environment.

In accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures for the accelerated development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated January 5, 2019, No. PF-5611, comprehensive measures are being implemented to develop tourism as a strategic sector, ensuring diversification of the national economy, regional development, job creation, raising the population's income and standard of living, and enhancing the country's investment attractiveness. In this regard, the improvement of foreign language skills, as well as the development of personnel training systems, qualification enhancement, and staff development in tourism through attracting foreign specialists to the educational process, increasing the number of educational institutions in regions, and expanding the list of specialties for personnel training, is crucial.

The process of personnel training is an important pedagogical task. The goal of enhancing students' pragmatic competence is to acquire practices as a means of professional communication. As Malev notes [1; 310-314], "professional communication means

communication at the workplace, international conferences, and professional presentations. Professional speech involves the use of formal terms and professional ethical norms, integrating youth and directing information exchange with professional relevance. In the process of exchanging knowledge, it is important to observe organizational norms of communication and roles of mutual understanding among participants." Stanton asserts that "effective professional communication requires clarity to ensure proper understanding of messages. This involves using pragmatic competence to avoid technical jargon and present the expected context."

1. Professional speech is aimed at achieving specific goals, such as transmitting information, making decisions, solving problems, or establishing relationships. Messages are created considering the set goals, and communication strategies are chosen to achieve them.
2. During communication, specialists must pay attention to their listeners, considering their knowledge level, interests, and needs, and adapt communication to ensure mutual understanding.
3. Effective professional communication involves attentive listening and cognitive transmission of information, engaging in constructive communication to achieve pragmatic competence.

Preparing students for communication in a foreign language requires mastering specialized knowledge, skills, and qualifications. These are usually studied as part of pragmatic competence. When teaching a course (English for Specific Purposes), communicative competence is seen as a set of skills related to successful communication, considering the scientific differences in communication. Language skills training should include vocabulary related to scientific concepts. Students should be taught to use different forms of communication, such as analyzing scientific articles, writing research papers, presenting results, and participating in discussions with colleagues. To improve pragmatic competence, a system of professionally-oriented communication situations should be created.

A competency-based system is implemented based on an approach that assumes extensive use of active and interactive lessons included in the educational process of non-linguistic higher education programs. Analyzing scientific sources shows that, in the process of teaching English, students must generalize personal learning experience, improve the content of professional and pragmatic competence using innovative systems. These systems have been tested in the teaching of students in the field of "Chemistry," and specific features of English language teaching have been identified. They define the content, strategy, and forms of lesson work and implement them [2; 77].

While non-linguistic specialists need to understand the content of pragmatic competence to effectively communicate in this field, it is crucial for instructors to ensure students have a clear understanding of the key concepts, theories, and principles. A foreign language is not only a means of communication and science but also a tool for developing various professional competencies necessary for specialists in various fields. Additionally, students learn to work with documents, interpret data in graphs, tables, and charts. Competencies are developed for negotiating with representatives from different fields, giving presentations to specialized audiences, and planning and implementing projects. The process is based on the following principles [3; 140].

Interdisciplinary Principle: Pragmatic competence involves the ability to correctly use language in different social-scientific situations. For effective professional communication, students must have specific knowledge of the subject, and in teaching English, practical use of professional knowledge is expected. In learning a foreign language, this includes not only understanding the literal meaning of words and grammar but also recognizing the scientific nuances of communication. Additionally, the lack of language and speech resources undoubtedly encourages students to enrich their professional knowledge, which helps develop pragmatic competence.

Principles of Critical Thinking Technology: Critical thinking is particularly important in ESP courses, especially when assessing pragmatic competence in the context of subject interconnections. Critical thinking is understood as influencing the contextual analysis of factors such as scientific norms, power dynamics, and interpersonal relations. In pragmatic competence, this includes understanding contextual factors and the correct cognitive interpretation of meaning behind language use. The study examines the study of pragmatic competence among subjects and interpretation of scientific information necessary for managing various scientific situations.

Principle of Considering the Level of Thought Development: Pragmatic competence includes understanding implicatures — implied, yet not explicitly stated meanings. When working with information, students make critical conclusions, helping to uncover hidden meanings through a chain of mental operations at the knowledge level. The article uses the classification of cognitive levels proposed by American psychologist Benjamin Bloom and other researchers, known as Bloom's taxonomy [4; 67]. In the context of ESP, Bloom's taxonomy can serve as a valuable foundation for developing learning objectives, assessing students' mastery, and fostering critical thinking adapted to specific fields and subjects. Students use their knowledge and understanding to solve problems or complete tasks related to their area. In non-linguistic fields, this is necessary for writing reports, analyzing practical research, conducting investigations, or performing specific procedures. At the implementation and evaluation stage, students should be able to logically and clearly present information, understand knowledge, analyze their work, and assess results [5; 99].

Students analyze complex information and break it down into components. For example, students studying scientific English may analyze experimental data or evaluate research results. They critically assess data, evidence, or methodologies in their field. They pay attention to the justification, reliability, and authenticity of sources and draw conclusions. Each participant in the discussion should actively engage in the process with pragmatic competence, using the full scientific and practical potential, resorting to various tactics. Most importantly, the methods created should be as effective and authentic as possible.

Principle of Local and International Scientific Equality: The principle of local and international scientific equality is a leading concept in this field, which provides an opportunity to use platforms for financing pragmatic competence resources and cooperation in science and knowledge. Specialists in this area acknowledge and respect the diversity of scientific views, methodologies, and research practices. This principle encourages openness to various ideas and research styles while recognizing a particular approach or perspective. For example, students will not face difficulties when describing London or the Navruz holiday, but describing

laboratory equipment or lacking knowledge and information in this area may lead to certain difficulties in professional activities.

Principle of Simplicity: Simplifying ESP courses and their focus on the field aims to enhance students' attention to language skills and content. The curriculum is structured to optimize the learning process in limited time, prioritizing terms and communication strategies critical for professional success. Often, this requires a quick response to emerging problems. In such situations, it is essential to consider their specifics and accurately describe the scope of pragmatic competence in speech.

Principle of Considering Expert Opinion in Creating Situations: An English language instructor cannot fully master all the theoretical and practical materials in their field. Situations should be created in close collaboration not only with instructors but also with industry representatives. Chemistry, as one of the fastest-growing fields, requires constant contact with industry specialists to ensure the educational materials and problem situations correspond to real-life scenarios.

Professionally Oriented Scientific Situations for Non-Linguistic Fields in English Courses include the following crucial elements [5; 67]:

- Creating a visual environment and using audio materials, employing interactive virtual resources, engaging industry specialists, considering interdisciplinary interaction.
- Creating conditions for the successful development of scientific-professional competence and perception, evaluating results.

Students should remember that the instructor may not have sufficient knowledge in the specific field. English instructors should be flexible, willing to listen to students, adapt their professional interests, and show readiness to take risks [6].

Creating ESP courses for students is a complex task that requires time from the perspective of pragmatic competence. Course developers should focus on students' needs and interests. However, due to the lack of ready-made materials for ESP courses, they must be carefully planned and adapted. Course materials should match the audience and adhere to the principle of scientific equality, a leading concept in science and academic integrity, promoting collaboration and mutual respect between scientists and researchers from various countries and regions. The course developer or ESP instructor designing a course or writing study materials should utilize their research results and be confident in understanding these skills. They should focus on communication with students without overloading the course with a list of terms and tedious grammar exercises.

Pragmatic competence in English for Specific Purposes means the ability to effectively and scientifically deliver specialized language training to meet the needs and goals of students within a given time. The ESP instructor should strive to solve problems in this context by offering the following stages:

- Defining, evaluating, and outlining the problem;
- Mastering pragmatic and professional communication skills;
- Initiating initial discussions and negotiations between interested parties;
- Ensuring adequacy of scientific and professional connections;
- Analyzing scientific literature;
- Teaching teamwork;

- Revising or revisiting the initial problem statement;
- Choosing applicable research methods;
- Defining the existing evaluation process;
- Implementing the project;
- Conducting a general project evaluation;
- Applying knowledge and methods for intellectual and scientific development, enhancing professional skills, and self-improvement;
- Enhancing readiness for societal development based on the principles of humanism, knowledge, and democracy.

Improving students' pragmatic competence implies a broad range of academic and extracurricular activities within the framework of educational pragmatic orientation. However, these recommendations are proposed for use in general areas. The system proposed by Xo can be used to address issues arising during course design. Analyzing the main objective of the educational process in higher education, the researcher highlights three levels of interaction in learning between students and instructors:

1. Individual
2. Interpersonal
3. Social and personal [7; 311-315].

Thus, the goal of this study (needs analysis) is to identify students' high interest in participating in newly proposed courses, which also confirms their satisfaction with the existing course, which was designed by the researcher with various activities.

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